

Public Perspectives on AI Governance: A Survey of Working Adults in California, Illinois, and New York

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Abstract

This report presents findings from a March 2025 survey examining public attitudes toward specific artificial intelligence (AI) policy objectives among working-class adults in three US states: California, Illinois, and New York. The survey collected responses from 300 participants, measuring their degree of support for 18 specific AI regulatory proposals. A majority of respondents expressed support for 17 of the 18 proposals with 75% of all responses indicating “support” or “strong support” for the policy objectives (80% and 67% for liberal- and conservative-leaning respondents respectively). Respondents had the highest level of average support (91%) for content-labeling measures and the lowest average support (38%) for proposals to slow the overall pace of AI development.¹

1 Methodology

1.1 Survey Design

See Appendix A for the full survey.

The survey was designed to assess public attitudes toward specific AI governance proposals. We selected a set of 18 questions about policy objectives based on a review of existing and proposed AI governance frameworks including the [EU AI Act](#) (passed Mar. 2024), [NIST AI RMF](#) (released Jul. 2024), [California’s SB 1047](#) (vetoed Aug. 2024), and [US Executive Order 14110](#) (rescinded Jan. 2025), Illinois’s [HB 3506](#) (proposed Feb 2025), and New York’s [RAISE act](#) (proposed Mar 2025).

All questions on policy preferences were formulated as policy proposals using a 5-point Likert scale with options “strongly oppose” (1), “oppose” (2), “neutral” (3), “support” (4), and “strongly support” (5). All questions were framed in terms of a pro-regulatory statement such that a response of 1 always indicated opposition to policy action and a response of 5 always indicated support for policy action. We designed questions to describe policy objectives in a way that is accurate, clear, and minimally biased. To mitigate biases due to question framing, we prompted ChatGPT-o4-mini to offer feedback on the neutrality of question framing. A transcript of ChatGPT-o4-mini’s feedback on our survey wording is available [here](#). On a rating scale from 0 to 10 where 0 indicates anti-regulatory bias, 5 indicates balance, and 10 indicates pro-regulatory bias, ChatGPT-o4-mini offered a median rating of 5 and a mean rating of 5.39.

We also asked respondents 9 demographic questions to study trends in views on AI policy proposals. Finally, we used an attention check (question number 15) asking respondents to select “Neutral.” Fortunately, all 300 responses passed this attention check.

¹See the full survey administered to participants in Appendix A. Raw data can be downloaded at [this link](#).

Figure 1: Support for AI policy proposals by state.

1.2 Survey Administration

The survey was not necessarily conducted on a representative sample of adults for the states of California, Illinois, and New York. Participants were knowledge workers recruited through the [CloudResearch](#) online survey platform. CloudResearch [reports](#) that workers earn an average of \$10 per hour. We paid \$3 for each completed survey which took respondents a median of 4 minutes and 31 seconds to complete. In March 2025, we surveyed 100 adults from each of three US states: California, Illinois, and New York which were selected because of ongoing state-level legislative debates surrounding AI policy in 2025. Participants represented varying levels of AI familiarity and technological literacy, as well as different professional sectors and geographic locations.

2 Results

The full results can be downloaded at [this link](#). This data does not contain personally identifying information according to the US Department of Labor’s [definition](#).

2.1 Support for AI policy proposals by state

Figure 1 summarizes support for each AI policy proposal in each state. The survey revealed consistent support for AI governance policies across all three states, with relatively minor variations in specific policy preferences.

2.2 Support for AI policy proposals by political orientation

Figure 2 summarizes support for each AI policy proposal for liberal, moderate, and conservative respondents. We asked respondents for their political orientation using the options: “very liberal”, “somewhat liberal”, “moderate”, “somewhat conservative”, “very conservative”, and “prefer not to

Figure 2: Support for AI policy proposals by political identification.

say”. In Figure 2, we consider very/somewhat liberal respondents to be “liberal” and very/somewhat conservative respondents to be “conservative.” Liberals are the most supportive of AI policy proposals while conservatives are the least. However, all groups are broadly supportive of policy proposals.

2.3 Support for policy objectives by demographic groups

We asked respondents for their age, gender, educational attainment, employment status, industry of work, familiarity with AI, interaction frequency with AI, political orientation, and location. Figure 3 summarizes overall support for policy objectives by each demographic group. All groups for all demographics that we surveyed express support on average for AI policy action.

Disclosures

This research was funded and conducted under the [Machine Learning Alignment and Theory Scholars \(MATS\)](#) program. MATS did not offer any methodological input or assistance. Aside from MATS and MIT, this work was not conducted with any other organization’s influence, knowledge, or affiliation. Before this work had concluded, SC began an unrelated research residency at the UK AI Security Institute.

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Figure 3: Average support for AI policy proposals by demographic groups. Error bars show the standard error of the mean.

A Full Survey Administered to Participants

AI Policy Perspectives Survey

Thank you for participating in this survey on artificial intelligence policy perspectives. We are a team of independent researchers working to learn more about public opinion on AI policy. We have no political or industry affiliations. Your input will help us understand public attitudes toward various regulatory approaches.

This survey has 28 total questions and will take approximately 10 minutes to complete. Your responses will remain anonymous and will be used solely for research and educational purposes.

Defining frontier AI:

Many of the questions below refer to “frontier AI systems.” We use “frontier” to describe the most advanced and powerful AI systems available today. Regulators can classify systems as “frontier” based on how they perform on evaluations or how much they cost to develop.

In a nutshell: “frontier” AI = “state-of-the-art” AI

1. **AI Office:** The government should establish an AI office to study AI’s impacts on society, evaluate frontier AI systems for risks, and make non-binding recommendations to AI developers about how to reduce societal risks.
 - Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
2. **Funding:** Governments should establish programs for funding scientific research on understanding and mitigating the societal risks of AI.
 - Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
3. **System registration:** Companies who make frontier AI systems should be required to register those systems with the government.
 - Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
4. **Risk-management policies:** Companies developing frontier AI systems should be required to write and publicly share reports on their company policies for assessing and managing societal risks.
 - Strongly oppose
 - Oppose

- Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
5. **System documentation:** AI companies should be required to write and publicly share reports about what uses their frontier AI systems are designed for and how they are meant to behave.
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
6. **Risk assessment reports:** AI companies should be required to write and publicly share risk assessment reports for their frontier systems.
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
7. **Third-party evaluations:** AI companies building frontier models should be required to have a third party evaluate them for risks and publicly share a report on their findings.
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
8. **Government approval:** Companies developing frontier AI systems should be required to submit reports on risk evaluations and obtain government approval from a designated AI office before deploying their systems.
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
9. **Safety requirements:** Government AI agencies should have the authority to make and enforce concrete safety standards for frontier AI systems.
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
10. **Staged deployment:** Companies deploying frontier AI systems should be required to deploy them gradually in stages and monitor impacts at each stage. For example, developers could be required to first release a system with limited access to users before giving users full access later.

- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
11. **Content labeling:** To inform humans about what kind of content they are viewing, AI-generated content (images, videos, text) should be required to be clearly labeled as AI-generated.
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
12. **File labeling:** To help track the origins of data (known as digital forensics), regulators should require that AI-generated content (images, videos, text) are saved using file formats which indicate that they are AI-generated.
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
13. **Shutdown procedures:** AI companies building autonomous frontier AI systems should be required to report on what, if any, shutdown procedures they have in place for them.
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
14. **Whistleblower protections:** Policymakers should establish legal protections for employees of AI companies who raise concerns about company risk management practices or report potential violations of laws.
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
15. **Checking in:** Please answer “Neutral” to this question.
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
16. **Incident reporting:** AI companies building frontier models should be required to publicly report on incidents which involve harms to humans health or large economic damages.

- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
17. **Direct liability:** AI companies should be held liable for direct harms caused by their systems as if those systems were their employees.
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
18. **Indirect liability:** Companies that make frontier AI systems should be held legally responsible for indirect damages their systems cause if a court establishes that the company could have anticipated these problems.
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support
19. **Slower development:** Should governments work to slow down the development of AI until we have more protections in place to reduce risks, even if it delays benefits of the new technology?
- Strongly oppose
 - Oppose
 - Neutral
 - Support
 - Strongly support

Demographic Questions:

Please provide the following information about yourself:

1. Age range:

- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65+
- Prefer not to say

2. Gender:

- Female
- Male

- Non-binary
 - Prefer not to say
3. Highest level of education completed:
- Less than high school
 - High school graduate or equivalent
 - Some college, no degree
 - Associate's degree
 - Bachelor's degree
 - Master's degree
 - Professional degree
 - Doctorate
 - Prefer not to say
4. Employment status:
- Employed full-time
 - Employed part-time
 - Self-employed
 - Unemployed
 - Student
 - Retired
 - Unable to work
 - Prefer not to say
5. What industry sector(s), if any, do you have work experience in? (if employed):
- Technology/IT
 - Healthcare
 - Education
 - Finance/Banking
 - Government/Public Sector
 - Manufacturing
 - Retail
 - Other (specify): _____
 - Not applicable
 - Prefer not to say
6. Familiarity with AI technology:
- Not at all familiar
 - Slightly familiar
 - Moderately familiar
 - Very familiar
 - Extremely familiar
7. How often do you interact with AI systems such as ChatGPT in your daily life?
- Almost never
 - Approximately monthly

- Approximately weekly
- Approximately daily or more

8. Political orientation:

- Very liberal
- Somewhat liberal
- Moderate
- Somewhat conservative
- Very conservative
- Prefer not to say

9. Geographic region:

- Urban
- Suburban
- Rural